

How Social Media Revenue Models Incentivize Misinformation

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ABSTRACT

The spread of misinformation on online social media networks has become a concern. This research focuses on the connection between revenue models, incentives and the dissemination of misinformation on these platforms. Two methods implemented: a literature review on the revenue strategies of platforms like Facebook and TikTok. A comparative case study on the spread of misinformation on social media to find the way these platforms incentivize the spread of false or misleading content.

Results show that revenue models driven by user engagement and advertising revenue amplify misinformation. Algorithms that aim to maximize user interaction tend to prioritize sensational and emotionally charged content. Monetizing user data contributes to the creation of environments where users are exposed to a limited range of information, reinforcing existing biases and beliefs.

Options to mitigate the impacts of misinformation. Increased transparency from these platforms regarding their algorithms and data practices, stronger regulations that hold platforms accountable, and the development of digital literacy programs to empower users to critically evaluate information.

Keywords

Misinformation, user engagement, incentives, social media, revenue models.

INTRODUCTION

This report is based on social media platforms and their revenue models. The aim is to figure out if the revenue models of social media platforms are arranged in a way that encourages the spread of misinformation. Furthermore, what kind

of positive engagement these kinds of platforms get from it. A few experts found out via eye tracking software on social media platforms facebook and twitter, that people gaze more at misinformation than information that is true and fact-checked (Ladeira, W. J., Dalmoro, M., Santini, F. de O., & Jardim, W. C., 2021). This research was based on brands, but fake news is being used within a variety of subjects such as; Elections (Allcott, H., & Gentzkow, M., 2017), Warzones (Kreft, J., Boguszewicz-Kreft, M., & Hliebova, D., 2023) and overall misinformation posts.

It can be rightfully said that misinformation is a problem in the social media world as of today. But the different reasons for why somebody would post misinformation are far from the same. For example, misinformation about the elections can be used to make the opposite party look bad in the eyes of the voters. The same applies to propaganda strategies in war zones, where the truth is often obscured, leading people to perceive reality differently than it actually is. Now the question is if the revenue models of social media platforms encourage this behavior of people to exploit misinformation.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

This research will evaluate the knowledge gap between the revenue models of social media and if they encourage the spread of misinformation. As time of publishing a lot of articles talk about how misinformation gets more engagement and getting their users to talk about it on social media (Ladeira, W. J., Dalmoro, M., Santini, F. de O., & Jardim, W. C., 2021). On the other hand, there are the revenue models of social media which are outlined and businesses know how to generate revenue from it. This presents the way the revenue model operates and encourages people and businesses to create and spread posts with misinformation. It gets more engagement, attention, views, and watch time. What does get talked about

is how social media platforms are trying to get rid of misinformation via AI search engines or stricter policies.

To narrow this research down the focus will be on the western social media users to get a more accurate understanding of a specific target group instead of everyone. As mentioned earlier there are many forms of misinformation that are used in today's world, this is being researched by numerous institutes and people. On the other hand there are ways to make online revenue by getting views, watch time, and user engagement (Singh, M. K., Ahmed, J., Alam, M. A., Raghuvanshi, K. K., & Kumar, S. 2023). This can be done through social media platforms such as; Facebook, X (Before twitter), TikTok, Youtube, etc.

The focus area of social media platforms within this research will be the top three most used social media platforms which are used in the western society. As of today, November 2024, those platforms are Meta (Facebook, Whatsapp, Instagram), Youtube and Tiktok. These platforms have the most active users per month in the western world. These social media platforms all have revenue models which are set up in different ways and have different requirements to generate revenue from a post. Facebook will be used as the main revenue model to make it easier to analyse the data. This can be used to make a comparative study between different social media platforms, which helps to understand the dynamics between the revenue model, the incentives and the spread of misinformation.

Scoping down the research of social media use in the western world is helpful because of the difference in app usage in other parts of the world. The findings of this study can be valuable for social media platforms to fight against the misinformation that is being spread across their own platforms.

METHOD

This paper's study starts with a structured literature review of common revenue models used by social media platforms in the western market. The review focuses on scientific articles and industry reports to identify and analyze common social media revenue models and define key factors. A systematic search was conducted using the search terms "revenue models", "social media incentives", "advertising revenue", and "engagement-based algorithms" to identify relevant sources. From this analysis, a framework is developed to later evaluate how each revenue component might amplify with the findings of a

comparative case study (more on this later). This framework provides structured categories of incentives, creating a benchmark against which case study findings can be assessed.

The case studies were identified through a systematic search of peer-reviewed journal articles, using the search terms "misinformation", "user engagement", "fake news", "social media", "TikTok", "Facebook", "vaccine misinformation" and "COVID-19". Articles were selected based on their relevance to the spread of misinformation on social media platforms within the Western market, their focus on user engagement patterns or platform-specific dynamics, and their publication in credible, peer-reviewed sources. Additionally, only studies providing detailed information on data collection and analysis were considered to ensure meaningful integration into this research.

Based on these criteria, three papers were identified focusing on the spread of misinformation. The first one, "#Coronavirus on TikTok: user engagement with misinformation as a potential threat to public health behavior" (Baghdadi et al., 2023), investigates how user engagement with misinformation on TikTok may influence public health behavior. This research investigates the characteristics of misinformation content and its interaction with user demographics and engagement patterns. The second case, "Understanding User Profiles on Social Media for Fake News Detection" (Shu et al., 2018), examines the relationship between user engagement behaviors and the dissemination of fake and real news. The study focuses on identifying explicit and implicit user characteristics that contribute to the spread of misinformation. The third case, "Quantifying the impact of misinformation and vaccine-skeptical content on Facebook" (Allen et al., 2024), explores how misinformation and vaccine-skeptical content are distributed and consumed on Facebook. The research investigates patterns of exposure to flagged and unflagged content and examines its potential to influence public understanding of COVID-19 vaccines.

To compare the findings from the revenue models research with the selected case studies, this paper aims to find correlations between the case studies by using the framework to categorize them. Using this framework, the study systematically analyzes the case studies by mapping them onto these predefined categories. This comparison method facilitates a structured evaluation of how the characteristics of revenue models intersect with the dynamics of the spread of misinformation described in the case studies. By cross-referencing the two, this approach ensures a consistent and

methodologically rigorous foundation for the later discussion and conclusion sections.

RESEARCH QUESTION

Within this research paper, the question “To what extent do the revenue models of social media platforms incentivize the spread of misinformation?” is central. Giving structure to this research question, there is the aim to answer the main research question by using three sub-questions which in part are able to partly answer the research question and collectively synthesize the answer. Firstly, the impact of revenue streams “To what extent do specific revenue streams such as advertising and data monetization incentivize the creation and sharing of information on social media platforms?” Secondly, from the user perspective the question is added: “How do platform algorithms designed to maximize engagement and revenue contribute to the spread of misinformation?”. Lastly, the correlation between revenue models and spreading of misinformation “What correlations exist between the revenue models of social media platforms and the amplification of misinformation?”.

CONCEPTUAL MODEL & THEORY

The conceptual model presents the relationship between the variables. For this research, the relationship between the three variables: revenue model of social media platforms, incentives and the spread of misinformation was explored. It is important to note that this paper aims to explore the direct relationship between the revenue models on social media platforms, the incentives and the spread of misinformation. The conceptual model positions "incentives" as a mediator, illustrating how revenue models on social media platforms create specific incentives that in turn lead to the spread of misinformation. It is important to note that social media is a contextual factor for all three variables. To explore this correlation it is important to define each variable and the contextual factor.

Figure 1: Conceptual model

To understand the first independent variable, it is crucial to understand the revenue model and the contextual factor (social media platforms) for this research. Hence, these two will be defined separately. There is only one independent variable as social media platforms are seen as a contextual factor for this research.

To define social media platforms: According to Rosário and Dias (2023b, pp. 1–2), “From a business perspective, social media platforms enable interactions between customers and companies, build relationships, and develop experiences that promote purchasing decisions (Bajpai et al., 2012).” D’Andrea et al. (2012, p. 109) stated that “the most important scope to join a Social Network is the possibility for consumers and companies to connect each other and to fulfill their specific needs for information sharing and interaction”. Based on these prior definitions, the social media platforms in this article are defined as “A social media platform is an online platform where information is shared between users to facilitate social relationship building and interaction between users.”

The revenue models are defined as “the specific modes in which a business model enables revenue generation”, according to Amit and Zott (2001, p. 515). Whereas, Rapaccini (2015, p. 1250) defines a revenue model as “the way through which the amount of money to be paid for the received services is determined”. Johnson et al. (2008, p. 62) as cited by Linde et al. (2021, p. 84) describe it as “how much money can be made: price x volume”. Based on these prior definitions, the revenue models in this article are defined as “A revenue model determines the revenue sources, the volume and distribution, which results in the revenue generated from the selected platform.”

To clarify this definition for revenue models, it is necessary to define volume and distribution. Volume is further defined as user engagement. According to Gandhi et al. (2023, p. 1418), it can be defined as: “the measures of user engagement (UE) in terms of the number of likes,

comments, and shares”. This is inline with the definition for volume used in this research. Distribution is further defined as algorithms. According to Guess et al. (2023, p. 398), algorithms can be defined as follows: “algorithms are personalized on the basis of many factors, such as a user’s past behavior and predictions derived from the actions of similar users, which leads to complex and potentially heterogeneous effects on content ranking.”. This is inline with the definition for distribution in this paper.

Incentives can be defined as “the motivation that a user requires to generate content”. To elaborate, there are multiple ways of motivating a social media user to generate and post content on a social media platform. For this research, it will be limited to two ways. The first is monetary-based incentive, which is represented in terms of financial gain. According to Saurwein and Spencer-Smith (2020, p. 823) “Economically motivated publishers have much in common with the producers of clickbait: they earn money from pay-per-click advertising on their websites”. The other is an algorithm incentive that is represented in terms of engagement on the platform. According to Maleki et al. (2023, p. 15) “incentives do affect user behavior, and greater adoption of this by social media platforms may turn the average social media user into a “citizen journalist” battling for eyeballs and engagement.”. Based on these prior definitions, the incentives in this article are defined as “*An incentive is an algorithmic or a monetary motivation provided by the platform to stimulate a user to share or post content on the platform.*”.

Lastly, the spread of misinformation is defined as, “Fake news is low-quality news that is created to spread misinformation and mislead readers. The consumption of news from social media is highly increased nowadays, as is the spreading of fake news.”, according to Shrestha and Spezzano (2019, p. 847). According to the Pew Research Center Barthel et al. (2016, p. 5), “64% of Americans believe that fake news causes confusion about the basic facts of current events, but often, they share news on social media without reading them to check the validity of the content.” Based on these prior definitions, the spread of misinformation in this paper is defined as “*The spread of misinformation is sharing of false information to and by the users on a selected platform.*”

To conclude, the definitions of the three variables display that the revenue model of social media platforms is an independent variable as it provides the framework for the mediator variable. To be specific, a framework for incentives to

motivate the users to share content on social media platforms through the monetary incentives and algorithms incentives in terms of engagement. Which in turn stimulates the spread of misinformation. Hence, the incentives have a mediating effect between the independent and dependent variables. The revenue model of social media platforms is an independent variable as it presents a framework in terms of the distribution of the information as volume x price increases revenue, which is linked to the incentives. The spread of misinformation is dependent on the revenue model of social media platforms and the incentives.

RESULTS

Revenue models

Social media platforms' revenue models are primarily driven by targeted advertising, which leverages user engagement to maximize ad exposure and profitability (Liu et al., 2022). This approach depends on collecting extensive data on users, including demographics, behavioral patterns, and engagement metrics, to create detailed user profiles (Sindermann et al., 2023). These profiles enable highly specific microtargeting, allowing advertisers to reach segmented audiences with tailored ads, which maximizes engagement and, consequently, ad revenue (Raffoul et al., 2023).

Advertising-based platforms, like Facebook and Twitter, boost profitability by promoting high-engagement, often sensational content that elicits strong user responses (Liu et al., 2022). This design choice amplifies content with high engagement potential, creating a feedback loop that promotes user retention and increases ad views (Sindermann et al., 2023). Thus, revenue strategy relies on a large user base and focuses on maximizing individual engagement, which may indirectly incentivize the spread of misleading or emotionally charged content due to its high engagement value (Sindermann et al., 2023).

Moreover, this revenue model raises significant privacy concerns. Facebook’s reliance on vast data collection practices, without direct user fees, has been linked to a model of “surveillance capitalism,” where user data is monetized to optimize ad targeting and platform engagement (Raffoul et al., 2023). This approach can result in filter bubbles and echo chambers, where users are continuously exposed to similar viewpoints, potentially reinforcing misinformation, as these personalized content feeds prioritize engagement

(Sindermann et al., 2023).

Using insights from Liu et al. (2022), Sindermann et al. (2023), and Raffoul et al. (2023), we developed a framework to categorize misinformation cases within ad-driven platforms, focusing on how engagement-based revenue models may amplify misleading content. The framework can be found in Appendix A.

Case study one: #Coronavirus on TikTok: user engagement with misinformation as a potential threat to public health behavior

The journal article explores the relationship between user engagement and misinformation on TikTok and its potential threat to public health behavior. The sample size was 1000 TikTok videos. From this sample size 166 videos (17%) met the criteria set by the researchers. twenty-six of these videos (16%) were posted by an official source. To specify, seven videos were from foundations or advocacy groups, six from governmental agencies, three from doctors, three from other healthcare providers, and one from a professional society. The other videos were divided as follows: seventy-six of the videos (46%) included humor, and ninety-one (55%) were set to music. fifty-five of the videos (33%) were published by women and ninety-three of the publishers (56%) were under the age of 30. Only two of the videos (1.2%) were suspected of commercial bias. Videos had a median views count of 8.4 million with a range of 4.9 million to 18 million. The full breakdown is shown in appendix B. (Baghdadi et al., 2023)

The results indicated that 119 videos out of the 166 (72%) were absent of misinformation. Thirty-six videos (22%) included a moderate amount of misinformation and eleven (7%) contained high levels of misinformation as is displayed in appendix C. According to Baghdadi et al. (2023, p. 3), “The relationship between misinformation and user engagement was complex. Videos that contained high levels of misinformation were less likely to be viewed but more likely to engage viewers. On the other hand, videos containing moderate misinformation were viewed as frequently as videos without misinformation but were less engaging.”. The research showed that the spread of misinformation related to public health increased, when the public health experts expressed uncertainty. Furthermore, it was concluded that misinformation spread more easily in comparison to true/valid information. (Baghdadi et al., 2023)

Case study two: User Trust and Engagement Patterns Analysis in Fake News Detection

This study investigates how user engagement patterns and profile features correlate with the dissemination of fake and real news, using datasets from BuzzFeed and PolitiFact. The results provide key insights into user behaviours, explicitly and implicitly, and their connection to the credibility of shared content.

Engagement Patterns; a small subset of highly active users disproportionately spreads both fake and real news, following a power-law distribution with $R^2 \geq 0.93$. BuzzFeed recorded 15,257 users with 25,240 engagements, while PolitiFact had 23,865 users with 37,259 engagements. Monitoring these hyper-engaged users is crucial for understanding fake news dynamics.

Explicit Profile Features; Verification Status; users sharing credible news are more likely to have verified accounts, higher follower counts, and a trust-follower-following (TFF) ratio greater than 1. **Account Age;** older accounts are more prone to sharing fake news, whereas newer accounts are associated with credible information, potentially reflecting improved digital literacy and access to fact-checking tools. **Follower-Following Ratio;** Users sharing real news often have a balanced or higher TFF ratio, indicating better network credibility and influence.

Implicit Profile Features: Age and Gender; older users tend to share fake news more frequently, while younger users prefer credible sources. A slight gender disparity was noted, with female users marginally more likely to share fake news. **Personality Traits;** users sharing real news score higher in extraversion and agreeableness, traits linked to network engagement and cautious sharing. Conversely, less extraverted users, who may interact within smaller, like-minded networks, are more inclined toward fake news.

Case study three: Quantifying the impact of misinformation and vaccine-skeptical content on Facebook

The third case study investigates the impact of widespread misinformation on Facebook related to COVID-19. The research included a section which researches the exposure to COVID-19 vaccine misinformation on Facebook. The article states that 13,206 URLs about the COVID-19 vaccine were shared publicly >100 times on Facebook during the initial three months of 2021. The URLs are checked by third-party

fact-checkers hired by the platform. The content that was flagged as misinformation received 8.7 million views and accounted for 0.3% of the 2.7 billion vaccine related URL views during that period. As is seen in the breakdown in appendix D. (Allen et al., 2024)

The study shows an overview of the number of views categorised in two main components, which each has three sub-groups. Flagged misinformation is divided in three groups: false with a view count between 3.0 million and 4.7 million, missing context with a view count between 2.6 million and 3.8 million, and lastly the mixture with a view count between 1.1 million and 2.1 million. The other main component is not flagged, which has three groups: not sent to fact-checkers with a view count around 2.7 billion, sent, but not rated with a view count between 34.9 million and 35.8 million, and true with a view count between 858.4 thousand (Allen et al., 2024).

The paper presents an example of an unflagged article, which is not directly providing misinformation, but it is misleading. To elaborate an article by the Chicago Tribune titled “A healthy doctor died two weeks after getting a COVID vaccine; CDC is investigating why.” Indicated uncertainty surrounding the true cause of death. However, the headline and story’s implicated that the vaccine may have been harmful to health. This has been identified as misleading or missing context by some scholars and journalists, who argue that it should be considered misinformation. This example reached 54.9 million users on Facebook (>20% of Facebook’s US user base) and the related URLs were viewed at least 67.8 million times (more than six times the number of views of all flagged misinformation combined). The top 10 stories (including the example) contained a similar amount of misleading information generated between 25.5 million and 67.8 million, which is shown in appendix E According to Allen et al. (2024, p. 4) *“Furthermore, little work has been done to identify these ambiguous stories in a systematic way at scale, compared with tracking outright falsehoods or content from low-credibility sources. This lack of scrutiny is meaningful: We find that exposure to vaccine-skeptical content far outstripped exposure to flagged misinformation.”* (Allen et al., 2024).

DISCUSSION

We can find correlations between the different aspects of the revenue models and the three different case studies by using the framework

found in appendix A that we created earlier and categorizing each case study according to key mechanisms, allowing for a structured interpretation of the results. The correlation results can be interpreted in figure 2.

CASE STUDY CORRELATIONS

	Case study 1	Case study 2	Case study 3
Data Collection and User Profiling		X	X
Algorithm-Driven Content Prioritization	X		X
Ad Revenue from High-Engagement Content	X		X
Privacy and Transparency Concerns			X

Table 1. Framework

Looking at the Data Collection and User Profiling, case study two demonstrates how explicit traits, such as account age and verification status, and implicit traits, like age and personality, influence engagement with fake and real news, showing that specific user characteristics drive misinformation dissemination. Similarly, case study three reveals how Facebook’s profiling mechanisms target segmented audiences with vaccine-skeptical content, emphasizing the connection between audience segmentation and exposure to misleading information. However, the precise profiling parameters in case study three remain unclear, which is addressed in the limitations of this research.

Interesting to see is how algorithmic prioritization thrives content with high engagement potential, as seen in case study one. It shows that emotional engaging content receives higher visibility regardless of accuracy. The same goes for case study three, where Facebook’s algorithm amplifies unflagged or ambiguous vaccine-related content, prioritizing high engagement even when the content is misleading. Both cases underscore the role of algorithm-driven prioritization in amplifying misinformation by leveraging user engagement as a primary metric.

Looking at the Ad Revenue from High Engagement Content, case study three explicitly highlights the connection between unflagged, misleading vaccine content and ad revenue on Facebook, as such content generates significant user engagement and boosts ad impressions. The same goes for case study one, where engaging videos, even those containing misinformation, indirectly contributes to its ad revenue by driving substantial viewer interactions.

At last, case study three highlights how

Facebook's lack of transparency in moderating unflagged vaccine-related content creates ambiguity for users. This limited visibility into content moderation enables misleading information to spread, raising concerns about platform

CONCLUSION & LIMITATIONS

The study of revenue models and the case studies in this research showed that the revenue models of social media platforms and incentives could indeed influence the spread of misinformation. By prioritizing user engagement and advertising revenue the platforms create an environment where sensational and emotionally charged content including misinformation, can be spread unchecked. The analysis of TikTok and Facebook showed how their algorithms actively contribute to the spread of misleading information by prioritizing content based on the number of likes, comments, and shares rather than the accuracy of the content.

The findings contribute to an understanding of this issue. There are some limitations of the study. Due to time constraints, specific platforms were chosen to be highlighted in the research. The limited number of platforms analyzed and the reliance on existing datasets may limit the generalizability of the findings.

Further research it is possible to dive into specific mechanisms underlying the spread of misinformation on various platforms. Furthermore research should be done into long term effects on individuals and society in general from exposure of misinformation.

Qualitative data collection should be considered. This data could be gathered from interviews with the representatives of the platforms, content creators, and users as it provides an in-depth insight on the topic. Another point of view such as the psychological or the social aspects can lead to a broader overview of the overall impact.

For policymakers a deep dive in regulations that would make the social media platforms responsible for what they publish is an interesting topic to explore. In this regard there could be strict rules on algorithmic transparency, data collection as well as mandatory fact-checking.

For social media platforms their business models and prioritize the dissemination of accurate information can be further explored. This could involve adjusting algorithms to prioritize reliable sources and providing users with tools to assess the credibility of content.

In conclusion, the research has shown the role that revenue models of social media platforms and the incentives play in the spread of misinformation. A multidisciplinary approach is necessary in order for this to be effectively analyzed, involving researchers, policymakers, and the companies behind the platforms. By building upon the findings presented here taking into consideration the limitations of the research there is space to take steps creating a healthier and more informative online environment.

REFERENCES

- Allcott, H., & Gentzkow, M. (2017). Social Media and Fake News in the 2016 Election. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 31(2), 211-236. <https://doi.org/10.1257/jep.31.2.211>
- Allen, J., Watts, D. J., & Rand, D. G. (2024). Quantifying the impact of misinformation and vaccine-skeptical content on Facebook. *Science*, 384(6699). <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adk3451>
- Amit, R., & Zott, C. (2001). Value creation in e-business. *Strategic Manage. J.*, 22(67), 493-520.
- Baghdadi, J. D., Coffey, K. C., Belcher, R., Frisbie, J., Hassan, N., Sim, D., & Malik, R. D. (2023). #Coronavirus on TikTok: user engagement with misinformation as a potential threat to public health behavior. *JAMIA Open*, 6(1). <https://doi-org.tilburguniversity.idm.oclc.org/10.1093/jamiaopen/ooad013>
- Bajpai, V., Pandey, S., & Shriwas, S. (2012). Social media marketing: Strategies & its impact. *International Journal of Social Science & Interdisciplinary Research*, 1(7), 214-223.
- Barthel, M., Mitchell, A., Holcomb, J., & Pew Research Center. (2016). Many Americans believe fake news is sowing confusion. https://assets.pewresearch.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/13/2016/12/14154753/PJ_2016.12.15_fake-news_FINAL.pdf
- D'Andrea, A., Ferri, F., & Grifoni, P. (2012). SNeM2S: a social network model for marketing strategies. *International Journal of E-Business Development*, 2(3), 103-110.
- Gandhi, M., Kar, A. K., & Roy, S. K. (2023). Managing industrial innovation communications on social media platforms for effective user engagement.

- Information Systems *Frontiers*, 26(4), 1417–1434.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10796-023-10402-9>
- Guess, A. M., Malhotra, N., Pan, J., Barberá, P., Allcott, H., Brown, T., Crespo-Tenorio, A., Dimmery, D., Freelon, D., Gentzkow, M., González-Bailón, S., Kennedy, E., Kim, Y. M., Lazer, D., Moehler, D., Nyhan, B., Rivera, C. V., Settle, J., Thomas, D. R., . . . Tucker, J. A. (2023). How do social media feed algorithms affect attitudes and behavior in an election campaign? *Science*, 381(6656), 398–404.
<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abp9364>
- Johnson, M. W., Christensen, C. M., & Kagermann, H. (2008). Reinventing your business model. *Harvard Bus. Rev.*, 86(12), 57-68.
- Kreft, J., Boguszewicz-Kreft, M., & Hliebova, D. (2023). Under the Fire of Disinformation. Attitudes Towards Fake News in the Ukrainian Frozen War. *Journalism Practice*, 1-21.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/17512786.2023.2168209>
- K. Shu, S. Wang and H. Liu, "Understanding User Profiles on Social Media for Fake News Detection," 2018 IEEE Conference on Multimedia Information Processing and Retrieval (MIPR), Miami, FL, USA, 2018, pp. 430-435.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/MIPR.2018.00092>
- Ladeira, W. J., Dalmoro, M., Santini, F. de O., & Jardim, W. C. (2021). Visual cognition of fake news: the effects of consumer brand engagement. *Journal of Marketing Communications*, 28(6), 681-701.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13527266.2021.1934083>
- Linde, L., Frishammar, J., & Parida, V. (2021). Revenue Models for Digital Servitization: A Value Capture Framework for Designing, Developing, and Scaling Digital Services. *IEEE Transactions On Engineering Management*, 70(1), 82–97.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/tem.2021.3053386>
- Liu, Y., Yildirim, P., & Zhang, Z. J. (2022). Implications of Revenue Models and Technology for Content Moderation Strategies. *Marketing Science*.
<https://doi.org/10.1287/mksc.2022.1361>
- Maleki, N., Padmanabhan, B., & Dutta, K. (2023). The Effect of monetary incentives on health Care Social media Content: Study based on topic modeling and sentiment analysis. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 25, e44307.
<https://doi.org/10.2196/44307>
- Rapaccini, M. (2015). Pricing strategies of service offerings in manufacturing companies: a literature review and empirical investigation. *Production Planning & Control*, 26(14–15), 1247–1263.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09537287.2015.1033495>
- Rosário, A. T., & Dias, J. C. (2023). Marketing Strategies on Social Media Platforms. *International Journal of E-Business Research (IJEBR)*, 19(1), 1-25.
<https://doi-org.tilburguniversity.idm.oclc.org/10.4018/IJEBR.316969>
- Saurwein, F., & Spencer-Smith, C. (2020). Combating disinformation on social media: multilevel governance and distributed accountability in Europe. *Digital Journalism*, 8(6), 820–841.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/21670811.2020.1765401>
- Shrestha, A., & Spezzano, F. (2019). Online Misinformation: From the Deceiver to the Victim. In 2019 IEEE/ACM International Conference on Advances in Social Networks Analysis and Mining (ASONAM), Vancouver, BC, Canada, pp. 847-850.
<https://doi.org/10.1145/3341161.3343536>
- Sindermann, C., Scholz, R. W., Löchner, N., Heinzlmann, R., & Montag, C. (2023). The Revenue Model of Mainstream Social Media: Advancing Discussions on Social Media Based on a European Perspective Derived from Interviews with Scientific and Practical Experts. *International Journal Of Human-Computer Interaction*, 1–17.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2023.2278292>
- Singh, M. K., Ahmed, J., Alam, M. A., Raghuvanshi, K. K., & Kumar, S. (2023). A comprehensive review on automatic detection of fake news on social media. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-023-17377->

APPENDICES

APPENDIX A:

FRAMEWORK FOR MISINFORMATION AND AMPLIFICATION ON SOCIAL MEDIA

Data Collection and User Profiling	
Mechanism	Social networks gather extensive user data, including demographics, behaviors, preferences, and social connections.
Potential impact	Detailed user profiling enables precise targeting, increasing the likelihood of sensational or misleading content reaching receptive and vulnerable audiences.
Algorithm-Driven Content Prioritization	
Mechanism	Social networks' algorithms prioritize content with high engagement potential, amplifying posts that generate reactions, shares, and comments.
Potential impact	Misinformation often elicits strong emotional responses, making it more likely to achieve high engagement and gain visibility, aligning with the platform's engagement-driven goals.
Ad Revenue from High-Engagement Content	
Mechanism	Social networks' ad revenue models rely on engagement metrics, where higher interactions lead to increased ad impressions and, consequently, greater revenue.
Potential impact	Content that drives significant engagement, including misinformation, indirectly supports revenue generation, creating an incentive to prioritize such content in algorithms.
Privacy and Transparency Concerns	
Mechanism	Social networks prioritize advertising efficiency over transparency, limiting user understanding of how their data is used and how content is curated.
Potential impact	A lack of transparency about data usage and content prioritization makes it difficult for users to identify why certain content, including misleading or false information, appears in their feeds, facilitating its spread.

APPENDIX B:

Table 1. Video views by characteristic and content

Video characteristics	Videos (%) <i>n</i> = 166	Median views (IQR)
Official publisher		
Healthcare worker	8 (5)	14M (13–14M)
Foundation/government	13 (4)	28M (19–35M)
News media/outlet	4 (2)	7.2M (5.2–9.2M)
Any official source ^a	26 (16)	23M (10–35M)
Unofficial publisher		
Patient	5 (3)	18M (14–21M)
Other	136 (82)	7.4M (4.4–11M)
Subject content		
Risk factors ^a	22 (13)	21M (13M–35M)
Symptoms ^a	26 (16)	16M (7.7M–37M)
Modes of transmission ^b	38 (23)	12M (6.4M–24M)
Prevention ^a	90 (54)	11M (5.6M–23M)
Content related to prevention		
Masks	60 (36)	9.5M (5.6M–22M)
Hand hygiene	53 (32)	8.4M (4.9M–27M)
Distancing	45 (27)	7.7M (4.7M–14M)
Quarantine/isolation ^a	35 (21)	5.0M (3.4M–11M)
Limiting exposures	51 (30)	9.5M (4.9M–23M)
Content related to masks		
Demonstration of use ^h	43 (26)	10M (7.1M–24M)
Positive sentiment	37 (22)	8.1M (5–18M)
Neutral sentiment	20 (12)	10M (7.3–37M)
Negative sentiment	3 (2)	5.0M (4.7–21M)
Content related to testing		
Testing discussed ^b	13 (8)	5.0M (3.7M–7.7M)
Positive sentiment	9 (5)	5.0M (3.7–7.7M)
Neutral sentiment	7 (4)	8.7M (5.1–20M)
Negative sentiment	0 (0)	–
Misinformation		
Absent	119 (72)	8.5M (5.3–19M)
Moderate	36 (22)	6.8M (3.6–16M)
High	11 (7)	9.4M (5.1–18M)
DISCERN rating		
Low ^b	50 (30)	9.9M (4.5–22M)
Moderate	84 (51)	9.9M (4.5M–22M)
High	32 (19)	8.2M (5.0M–15M)
PEMAT rating		
High understandability ^b	110 (66)	9.4M (5.4–21M)
High actionability	15 (9)	26M (5.6M–35M)
Total	166	8.4M (4.9M–18M)

Abbreviation: PEMAT: Patient Education Materials Assessment Tool.

^aSignificantly different than comparator group at an $\alpha < .001$.

^bSignificantly different than comparator group with *P*-value $< .05$.

(Baghdadi et al., 2023)

APPENDIX C:

Figure 1. User response to TikTok videos based on level of misinformation.

Table 2. Factors associated with view counts and comments indicating intention to change behavior on TikTok videos with the #Coronavirus hashtag

Factor	View count ^a IRR (95% CI)	Behavior change ^b OR (95% CI)
Predictor of interest		
Moderate misinformation	0.78 (0.57–1.05)	0.25 (0.078–0.77)
High misinformation	0.59 (0.39–0.90)	6.14 (0.72–52.6)
Publisher characteristics		
Publisher age < 30	0.57 (0.45–0.73)	0.40 (0.14–1.11)
Official source ^c	1.49 (1.09–2.05)	0.35 (0.045–2.71)
Video content		
Inclusion of humor	1.20 (0.93–1.55)	0.487 (0.18–1.28)
Content related to symptoms	1.72 (1.25–2.37)	3.18 (0.92–10.9)
Content related to testing	0.96 (0.61–1.50)	10.1 (2.25–45.5)
Content related to prevention	1.66 (1.31–2.09)	10.2 (3.46–29.8)
Content related to quarantine	0.50 (0.39–0.64)	0.14 (0.048–0.40)
Commercial bias	0.23 (0.15–0.35)	-omitted-
Video quality		
DISCERN rating of moderate-high	0.67 (0.51–0.89)	2.07 (0.66–6.46)
PEMAT understandability high	1.18 (0.92–1.50)	3.22 (1.24–8.34)
PEMAT actionability high	0.97 (0.64–1.46)	1.65 (0.14–19.4)

Bold values represent factors that were significant at a threshold of $\alpha < .05$.

^aView count was modeled using multivariable negative binomial regression.

^bBehavior change was evaluated based on user comments reporting intention to change behavior and was modeled using multivariable logistic regression.

^cGovernment, foundation, or advocacy group.

(Baghdadi et al., 2023)

APPENDIX D:

Fig. 2. Exposure to vaccine-related content on Facebook that was publicly shared >100 times on Facebook during the first 3 months of 2021. View counts are shown with 95% CIs to account for differentially private noise (see SM section S0.1.1 for more information). **(A)** Total views for misinformation versus non-misinformation content, broken down by fact-checker rating. The y axis is square-root-scaled for better visualization of misinformation content, which

received only 0.3% of vaccine-related views during this time period. **(B)** Total views of the top 10 most popular story clusters across all content, where story clusters are composed of similar URLs that have been clustered together on the basis of their headlines and descriptions (see SM section S0.1.2 for clustering details). The aggregate number of views on all misinformation URLs is indicated by the red dashed line.

(Allen et al., 2024)

APPENDIX E:

Fig. 4. Predicted impact on vaccination intentions of vaccine-related URLs that were publicly shared >100 times on Facebook during the first 3 months of 2021. **(A and B)** Distribution of predicted treatment effect on vaccination intentions across all URLs, comparing 186 URLs flagged as misinformation (shown in red) versus 13,020 URLs not flagged by fact-checkers (shown in blue). **(A)** Density plots for predicted treatment effects. Dashed lines represent the medians of the distributions. **(B)** The same histogram of URL treatment effects as in **(A)**, weighted by the number of views each URL received. Note that the y axis in **(B)** is shown on a square-root scale for better visualization. **(C)** Overall predicted treatment effect among the 3711 hesitancy-inducing URLs (i.e., predicted crowdsourced aggregate score below scale

midpoint), comparing the 183 URLs flagged as misinformation versus the 3528 URLs that were not flagged (which we refer to as vaccine-skeptical). Shown is the total impact across each type of URL, normalized by the number of US Facebook users. The point estimates (in black) are shown with 50 and 95% CIs, calculated from a parametric bootstrap of our coefficients. We additionally compute analytical prediction intervals, assuming worst-case correlation among errors, and find that our results are robust even under these extreme assumptions (see SM section S5.5). Note that for readability, the scales for flagged misinformation differ from vaccine-skeptical content; in the vaccine-skeptical panel, we label the average impact for flagged misinformation with a red dashed line for reference.

(Allen et al., 2024)